

Radon-222 entry rate in homes and workplaces determined with modern electronic radon detectors

Krasimir Mitev^a, Vladislav Todorov^a, Strahil Georgiev^a, Philippe Cassette^a, Benoit Sabot^b, Zornitza Daraktchieva^c, Stefan Röttger^d, Ivelina Dimitrova^{a,*}

^a Sofia University "St Kliment Ohridski" (SU), Faculty of Physics, 5 James Bourchier Blvd., Sofia, 1164, Bulgaria

^b Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, LIST, Laboratoire National Henri Becquerel (LNE-LNHB), Palaiseau, F-91120, France

^c UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA), CRCE, Chilton, Didcot, Oxon OX11, ORQ, United Kingdom

^d Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Bundesallee 100, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany

HIGHLIGHTS

- Radon entry rate in buildings can be measured using affordable electronic monitors.
- Radon time series allow parallel estimates of radon entry and air exchange rates.
- The novel approach was verified in a primary metrology lab and radon test beds.
- Radon entry rate was monitored remotely in 36 occupied homes and workplaces.
- New dynamic data on radon entry rate can empower smart indoor environment control.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Radon-222
Radon entry into buildings
Air change rate
Electronic radon detectors
Online monitoring
Radon in homes and workplaces

ABSTRACT

Radon is the second leading cause of lung cancer after smoking. While radon exposure is assessed by the annual average radon concentration, the radon entry rate, which is fundamental to understanding radon behaviour and mitigation, has received less attention due to measurement challenges. Technological advancements over the past decade have led to the development of affordable and widely available consumer-grade electronic detectors that can provide time-resolved radon measurements. A novel method for estimating the radon entry rate from radon time series measured by fast-response, consumer-grade electronic monitors is presented. It was validated through experiments conducted in a primary metrology laboratory and test-bed studies. It was implemented in a three-year radon monitoring campaign in 36 occupied dwellings and workplaces located in both radon-priority and non-priority areas. During the campaign data on the dynamics of radon entry rate and air change rate were gathered remotely without interrupting the buildings' usage cycle. A correlation between the radon entry rate and the air change rate at low ventilation was observed in about 80% of the buildings, which demonstrates that the radon entry rate can be studied in relation to other dynamic parameters. This new approach can be used by scientists developing models for radon transport in buildings, as well as by remediation and mitigation

* Corresponding author.

Email address: divelina@phys.uni-sofia.bg (I. Dimitrova).

professionals to provide smart and energy-efficient mitigation strategies. The method proposed herein provides insights into radon dynamics and can revolutionize our efforts to maintain a healthy indoor environment with respect to radon.

1. Introduction

Radon (^{222}Rn) is a naturally occurring invisible radioactive noble gas without taste or smell. It is the largest source of radiation exposure in homes for most of the population [1] and the second leading cause of lung cancer after smoking [2]. The European pooling study [3] showed a clear correlation between the increased radon exposure and lung cancer. The risk is higher in homes with an annual average radon activity concentration above 100 Bq/m^3 than in homes with radon levels below 100 Bq/m^3 . Based on this evidence, the World Health Organization [2] (WHO) recommended that countries set a national reference level for the annual average radon concentration in homes of 100 Bq/m^3 , but if this could not be achieved the reference level should not exceed 300 Bq/m^3 . Radon mitigation in existing buildings was recommended to reduce radon levels when the measured value exceeds the national reference level. Many countries developed extensive radon mitigation programs; however the United States is the undisputed leader in the number of buildings with radon mitigation [4]. The US National Radon Action Plan [5] set a goal to find, fix and prevent high indoor radon levels in 8 million buildings. If we extrapolate this number, the buildings requiring mitigation worldwide can be of the order of hundreds of millions.

The amount of radon in a building depends on many factors such as the radium content of the soil, the permeability of the ground, entry routes into the building, building materials, occupational patterns, ventilation rate, outdoor temperature, wind speed and direction, and outdoor pressure. Radon from the soil beneath enters buildings predominantly by advection, which is caused by the small pressure difference (a few Pascals [6]) between the inside and outside. The radon entry rate through the foundations is a product of the soil gas entry rate and radon concentration. In general, the accumulation of radon in indoor air can be modelled by two main concurrent processes - the flux from existing sources (soil beneath the building, building materials, water supply, gas supply and outdoor air) and the decrease due to air exchange. Different approaches have been developed to decrease radon accumulation and consequent exposure to occupants. The approach recommended by the US Environmental Protection Agency [7] is to significantly reduce radon entry. Since the main source of radon in buildings is the soil gas [2], this is usually achieved by soil suction which reduces the pressure gradient that drives radon inwards and also removes radon from the building foundation. A less common approach is to dilute indoor radon by forced positive ventilation which introduces air to keep the inside pressure high and to avoid increasing the radon entry rate.

Therefore, the radon entry rate is the fundamental quantity for the radon diagnostics of buildings and for the design and efficiency testing of radon reduction or mitigation techniques. Several models for radon entry into houses were developed [6,8]. Theoretically the subject is well understood and explored; however, given the complexity of the modelling (various phenomena need to be taken into account, which leads to a variety of input parameters in the models) there is a need for experimental data for validation of the models. Measurements of the radon entry rate were attempted in several case studies [9–19]. They provided invaluable information on the transport of radon in buildings, but involved quite expensive laboratory-grade radon detectors, qualified personnel, and additional procedures like separate measurements of the ventilation rate [9–12,14–16,18,19] and/or evacuation and depressurization of the building [13,17,19]. Moreover, some of these measurements are not representative of the radon entry rate during normal building usage. This, combined with the need for expensive

equipment and qualified personnel, likely explains why the radon entry rate is hardly ever measured.

The objective of this work is to show that radon entry rate can be estimated by measurements of radon time-series data with consumer-grade electronic radon monitors. In order to demonstrate that, we developed a method based on a simple model of radon accumulation [20], which uses long time series of radon data obtained with electronic detectors. The method was applied to radon data collected from occupied rooms without altering the existing ventilation, which was primarily natural. It is shown to identify intervals in which the whole radon increase function could be fitted successfully with the model allowing the simultaneous estimation of the radon entry rate and the air exchange rate. The method was validated through experiments in a primary metrology laboratory, test-bed studies, and a three-year radon measurement campaign in 36 occupied dwellings and workplaces in normal and radon-priority areas. We demonstrate that consumer-grade electronic radon monitors with fast response time not only can measure the average radon concentration [21], but also allow real-time monitoring of radon accumulation without interrupting the building's usage cycle. This new approach provides insights into radon dynamics and can revolutionize the design and operation of mitigation systems by providing information on the actual dynamic parameters governing radon accumulation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Model of radon accumulation

It is assumed that the activity concentration of ^{222}Rn in the air of a room C_A satisfies the following equation:

$$\frac{dC_A}{dt} = \frac{J}{V} - \lambda_{eff} C_A, \quad (1)$$

where J is the radon entry rate in Bq/h , V is the volume of air in the room in m^3 and λ_{eff} is its effective decrease constant in h^{-1} .

The entry rate accounts for different radon sources. The main source of indoor radon is radon-rich soil gas coming through the foundation of the building which is mixed with radon coming from other rooms or floors due to air exchange in the building and radon coming from the outdoors, which is an additive parameter [22]. In some cases, building materials, water or natural gas used in the household can contribute to indoor radon. It is assumed that the entry rate J does not depend on the activity concentration of ^{222}Rn in the indoor air. Such an assumption is justifiable, since the transport of radon through the foundation is mostly due to advection and is driven by pressure gradients [9]. Even if there is diffusive transport from the ground or building materials, the concentration of radon in the soil gas or in the voids of the building materials is typically much higher than that in the indoor air. Under such conditions the entry rate due to diffusion will vary little with the variation in the activity concentration of radon in the room.

The effective decrease constant of radon λ_{eff} also accounts for multiple mechanisms. These include the radioactive decay of radon and the decrease of radon due to air exchange with the outdoor air or with other rooms/floors. Indoor radon can also decrease due to absorption in some plastics [23], but these effects should be negligible in inhabited rooms. All these radon sinks are proportional to the radon activity concentration in the air and can be described by the second term in Eq. (1). In cases where the neighbouring rooms have similar radon activity concentration, the effective decrease constant will only account for radioactive decay and air exchange with the outside:

$$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_{222} + ACH, \quad (2)$$

where λ_{222} is the decay constant of ^{222}Rn and ACH is the air change rate expressed in h^{-1} which shows how many times the volume of the room air is exchanged in 1 h.

For an interval in which J and λ_{eff} remain constant, the solution of Eq. (1) is:

$$C_A(t) = \frac{J}{V\lambda_{eff}} (1 - \exp(-\lambda_{eff}t)) + C_A^0 \exp(-\lambda_{eff}t), \quad (3)$$

where C_A^0 is the initial radon concentration. Eq. (3) can be expressed as:

$$C_A(t) = C_A^\infty - C_A^\delta \exp(-\lambda_{eff}t), \quad (4)$$

where $C_A^\infty = J/(V\lambda_{eff})$ is the asymptotic activity concentration at infinite time, $C_A^\delta = C_A^\infty - C_A^0$ is the difference between the asymptotic and the initial activity concentration. The variables C_A^∞ , C_A^δ and λ_{eff} are the function parameters that we determine by fitting the experimental data. The radon entry rate per unit of air volume J/V can be determined as:

$$\frac{J}{V} = C_A^\infty \lambda_{eff}. \quad (5)$$

The simple model of radon accumulation represented by Eq. (1) has been used for many years to describe indoor radon activity [20]. The accumulation of radon in rooms is described similarly in more recent models of the radon transport in buildings (e.g. [24]), but with the separation of different radon sources and sinks, e.g. the convective and diffusive fluxes and the mutual exchange of air between different rooms. The same model was used for the estimation of the radon entry rate by fitting continuous data in other studies [17], but the asymptotic radon activity concentration was estimated by fitting regions with relatively constant activity concentration. The model has also been used to describe the accumulation of radon in small volumes in studies of radon exhalation from soil gas [25] or building materials [26].

There are also some situations in which this simple model is not applicable. For example, if the activity concentration in the air C_A is comparable to the activity concentration in the source (e.g. the cavities in the soil or building materials), the diffusion flux will depend on C_A and J cannot be considered constant. Such conditions might occur in basement shafts as well as in studies of radon exhalation from the soil or building materials. In such cases the models could be modified to account for the high radon activity in the volume, leading to processes like back diffusion [27]. Furthermore, the conditions in some rooms might vary too quickly to consider J and λ_{eff} constant and to describe radon accumulation by a simple analytical function. This might be the case in dwellings with substantial contributions from a pulse radon source, such as radon emanating from water or natural gas.

At low ventilation rates and more localized radon source the possible inhomogeneity of radon in the room due to the contribution from building materials should also be considered. Finally, it should be kept in mind that the entry rate J determined by the fitting with a simple model is the result of combining many underlying parameters into a single source. In some cases, it might be necessary to conduct measurements in separate rooms and outdoors to separate the contributions of sources inside and outside the room. In the rare cases where outdoor radon concentration is comparable to that indoors, it might not be possible to detect and fit the radon increase due to indoor sources. The above two problems also arise in traditional measurements of the average radon activity concentration with passive radon detectors.

2.2. Conducted laboratory tests and continuous monitoring in occupied rooms

The feasibility of the proposed approach was tested in two ^{222}Rn build-up exposures with primary radon emanation standards in the low level radon reference chamber at PTB (Physikalisch-Technische

Bundesanstalt, Germany). Two sources of the type IRSD [28] (Integrated Radon Source Detectors) allowing an absolute estimate of the radon entry rate were used. They had ^{226}Ra (radium) activity of 158.6 ± 1.7 Bq and 66.4 ± 0.5 Bq and were produced in PTB by thermal physical vapor deposition of $^{226}\text{RaCl}_2$ onto ion-implanted silicon detectors [29]. The ^{222}Rn nuclei can leave the source by recoil after the alpha-decay of ^{226}Ra . The silicon detector allows simultaneous determination of the activity of ^{226}Ra and of ^{222}Rn retained in the source and determines the emanation rate of radon from the source (^{222}Rn nuclei emitted per second) using the difference [28]. Each source was placed in a certified hermetic volume along with three consumer-grade radon detectors of the type RadonEye⁺² (RE⁺²), which followed the accumulation of radon. The entry rate of ^{222}Rn in the exposure volume J can be estimated as a product of the radon emanation rate and the radon decay constant. Each source was allowed to emanate radon into the hermetic chamber of PTB with a certified volume. The leakage of the chamber had been previously tested by blowing synthetic, aged air through the system with a mass flow controller. In this way, a radon entry rate traceable to the national standard for α -emitting sources (and therefore traceable to the International System of Units) was created and was compared to the results obtained by fitting the RE⁺² data with the model presented above.

In order to test the proposed method under controlled and at the same time realistic indoor conditions, we performed experiments in two test beds (empty rooms) at Sofia University (SU). The radon build-up in the rooms was successfully monitored by several RE⁺² detectors. The characteristic growth curve of radon was observed due to the natural radon entry rate in the rooms (J_{bg}). A source of ^{226}Ra produced by the Czech Metrological Institute with activity $A = 104.5$ kBq (reference date 1 May 2006) and emanation power $\epsilon = 0.998$ was used as an additional radon source. The source is a "flow-through" type with an inlet and outlet and when air is blown through it, the activity of ^{222}Rn generated inside is carried out with the flow-through gas. We have previously observed that the emanation power of the source is very stable. The source was placed in the respective test bed and a pump and a drying unit were connected to its inlet. The source was continuously flushed in the room and the radon entry rate (activity entering the air per second) was estimated as:

$$J_{ref} = \epsilon A \exp(-\lambda_{226}(t - t_{ref})), \quad (6)$$

where the decay constant of ^{226}Ra is used to correct for the decay of the source since the reference date t_{ref} .

Since the volumes of the rooms (respectively 19.19 m^3 and 27.44 m^3) are much bigger than the source volume (260 ml), it can be assumed that the whole activity generated by the source is transferred in the room air. We positioned the radon detectors far from the walls, floor and inlets and outlets of the room to avoid potential inhomogeneities. Experimental sessions with open and closed source were conducted, during which the rooms were kept closed, in order to have relatively low and constant ventilation rate. The rooms were intensively ventilated by opening the doors and windows between the sessions in order to start the follow-up with low radon activity concentration. The accumulation of radon during the sessions is described with the model presented above. The radon entry rate J estimated from the fits could be compared with the reference value provided by the source certificate.

The laboratory tests were designed to test the approach and the applicability of the RE⁺² detectors at known radon entry rates and realistic activity concentrations. While the tests at PTB were conducted in a hermetic chamber (with λ_{eff} equal to ^{222}Rn half-life), the tests at Sofia University were at an air change rate that was not predetermined. The performance of the approach and the electronic detectors at different air change rates were further tested in real occupied rooms. We monitored the ^{222}Rn activity concentration (C_A) in 36 rooms in homes and workplaces in Bulgaria using RE⁺² electronic detectors for periods ranging from 9 months to 3 years. We obtained time series containing temperature, relative humidity and 60-minute averages of C_A , recorded

every 10 min and transmitted over WiFi. The WiFi transmitted data was recorded in the SPIRAD Database [30] and monitored online. The data recorded in the internal memory was downloaded every 3 months (according to the producer the memory is sufficient for 1 year of data). At 7 locations we also positioned NetAtmo meteorological stations with an indoor module measuring the temperature, relative humidity, pressure, CO₂ concentration and noise and an outdoor module measuring the temperature and humidity. The radon entry rate estimates were based on the WiFi radon data, as it is recorded in 10-minute intervals and allows better follow-up of radon increases than the Bluetooth data recorded every hour. Intervals for which the WiFi data was missing or skipped a significant number of points were not used in the analysis. In one home, the gaps in WiFi data were frequent and long and we successfully used the Bluetooth data for the radon entry rate measurements. Homes and workplaces in the city of Sofia (with average indoor radon concentrations) and in the region of Buhovo (with elevated indoor radon [31]) were included in order to attempt measurements of the entry rate for different levels of radon and with different statistical fluctuations. The selected homes in Sofia were situated on either the first or second floor of multi-storey buildings, which are the dominant type of residential buildings in the capital. All homes in the region of Buhovo were one- or two-storey houses, which is representative of this region. Some buildings were built more than 50 years ago, while others were built in the last decade. The number of occupants also varied from 1 to 5 persons. Most radon monitors were placed in the living room, but in several cases the bedroom was chosen. This allowed us to test the approach under different conditions. By including workplaces in the study we also tested the approach under different ventilation patterns.

2.3. Electronic radon detectors

In the last decade, affordable consumer-grade electronic radon detectors have been spreading in the market. Several studies comparing different brands of such detectors have been published recently [32,33]. In the current study we used the RadonEye⁺² (RE⁺²) detector, which is a commercial device intended towards end-users for home monitoring [34]. The RE⁺² was selected for the experiments, because it has one of the highest sensitivities among similar devices [32] (of 2.25·10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ per Bq/m³) and a relatively fast response time [32,35] (of about 90 min). The RE⁺² was also found to be comparable in performance to research-grade electronic radon monitors in a recent study [36] and shown to have high accuracy [37] (e.g. lower spread between different devices). However, the device readings can deviate from the true value (up to 20–30% [37,38]) and calibration is necessary for more precise measurements. It connects to smartphones via Bluetooth and can be integrated into some smart home systems. It also reports data over a WiFi connection, which can be viewed remotely on the producer's website. The device is based on an ionization chamber which detects the alpha particles emitted by ²²²Rn and some of its short-lived progenies (²¹⁸Po and ²¹⁴Po) generated in the chamber volume. Radon progenies in the ambient air are prevented from entering the chamber by filtering. The device is not spectrometric and the build-up of ²¹⁰Po in its volume can increase the background signal over time. The latest model RE⁺² allows real-time measurements of radon concentrations that are typical for homes (according to the producer its measurement range is from 7 Bq/m³ to 9435 Bq/m³). The measurement duration cannot be changed and the detector only reports the radon activity concentration averaged over the last 60 minutes. This 60-minute moving average is reported every 10 minutes over the WiFi, while it is recorded in the detector memory every 60 minutes and can be downloaded via Bluetooth connection. Values of the temperature and relative humidity are also measured and reported by the RE⁺². A measurement uncertainty is not reported and separate devices are not individually calibrated by the producer.

We have calibrated each RE⁺² device used in the current work just before the start of the monitoring campaign. For 20 of the devices the calibration was conducted at the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA)

with exposure to radon activity concentration traceable to the primary radon standard at the Henry Becquerel National Laboratory (LNHB). The calibration factors of the 20 detectors, which are used to multiply and correct the reported value, ranged from 0.70 to 1.06 [38]. All devices were calibrated at Sofia University by parallel measurements with a reference monitor AlphaGUARD PQ2000 Pro Rn/Tn [21]. The calibration factors of the 20 devices calibrated both at UKHSA and Sofia University agreed very well [38]. All values for the radon entry rate, reported in the current work were corrected with the individual calibration factor of each device.

The initial background of 20 of the used detectors was estimated at (2.5±0.5) Bq/m³ by placing them for 10 days in a radon-free nitrogen atmosphere at UKHSA [38]. The linearity of the detectors was also studied and was found to be excellent below 3500 Bq/m³ [21]. A slight non-linearity, causing an underestimation of the reported values within 12%, was noticed in the range 3500 Bq/m³ - 7000 Bq/m³ [21]. In order to estimate the statistical uncertainty of a single measurement, the standard deviations of the reported values during several exposures at different constant activity concentrations were estimated. An empirical formula for the statistical uncertainty was obtained [38] and is used for the RE⁺² data in this work.

We also estimated the response function of RE⁺² devices in a series of dedicated experiments [21]. The response function is defined as the detector signal after an exposure to activity concentration following a quasi delta function. The response function was obtained by exposing RE⁺² to short rectangular pulses of radon activity concentration [21]. Then, the detector's response to activity concentration following any function $C_A(t)$ can be found by convolution of this function and the response function. The response function F_R can also be used in its discrete form and the signal $S(t_i)$ can be approximated with:

$$S(t_i) = \sum_{k=n-1}^0 C_A(t_i - k\Delta t) F_R(k\Delta t) \quad (7)$$

where Δt is the interval between the values of the response function and n is the number of sufficient points to describe it. Thus, the response function is non-zero only in the interval $(0, n\Delta t)$ and only the activity concentration in the interval $(t - n\Delta t, t)$ influences the signal at a moment t . For the response function of RE⁺² $\Delta t = 10$ min and $n = 20$. The response function [21] is used to model the signal from RE⁺² data reported every 10 min (i.e. the 60-minute moving average). Knowing the response function of an electronic radon detector is important for following dynamic processes.

2.4. Fitting of data

In the time series obtained by the RE⁺² monitors we looked for intervals of radon accumulation that could be described with Eq. (3), e.g. intervals with stable radon entry and ventilation rate. The time series consist of values of the radon activity concentration averaged for the last 60 min and recorded every 10 min. An uncertainty is assigned to each point using an empirical formula [38]. A small data set with series from occupied buildings was analyzed by an operator who visually selected intervals with increasing radon. The data in these intervals was fitted with the given function and the fit parameters were determined. The entry rate was estimated by Eq. (5).

A larger data set was processed by a specifically developed computer code that selects intervals that could be fitted well with the function in Eq. (3) and returns the fit parameters. The algorithm attempts to perform a fit starting at every point in the time series and to find the largest window (within some limit) for which the fit is good enough (e.g. the biggest window with constant radon entry and air change rate). The fitting was done with the function `curve_fit` from the `scipy` library [39] with the absolute uncertainty of the data points used as weights. This function returns the fit parameters along with their correlation matrix. The fit is discarded by the code if its parameters do not agree with the assumed model (e.g., are negative), the increase it describes is not statistically

significant or its shape is close to a step with short plateau (determined to be a fitting artifact). A fit is further discarded if the uncertainty of the fit parameters is high and its p-value, representing the probability of not rejecting the fit by a chi-squared test, is low. The threshold parameters of the algorithm were set empirically by an operator who examined the fits visually. When “good” fits are found in intersecting intervals, the algorithm prioritizes the longest fit or the fit with higher p-value in cases of equal lengths.

The code did not find all intervals with increases marked by the operator and the operator skipped some found by the code. The intervals identified by both the operator and the code did not have exactly the same start and end. However, there was very good agreement between the parameters of the fits in the corresponding intervals selected by both the operator and the code. In addition, the code was used for analysis of data from the experiments in the test beds at SU with an artificial radon source and its results were in agreement with the reference entry rate.

3. Results

3.1. Proof of concept experiments and radon entry rate determination under controlled conditions

3.1.1. Radon entry rate determinations in the PTB low level radon reference chamber (LLRRC)

The low activity IRSD sources [40] used in the PTB reference chamber allowed an absolute estimate of the radon entry rate (Fig. 1a) in the chamber where the RadonEye+² monitors were placed. The maximum radon activity concentrations achieved in the chamber were 55 Bq/m³ and 134 Bq/m³ (see Fig. 1b), which are common for indoor air. The data from RE+² detectors was fitted with the model (see Fig. 1c and d). The radon entry rate J estimated from the fits averaged for the three detectors is compared with the reference value provided by the IRSD sources in Table 1. The highest relative difference of the value of J estimated by a RE+² detector and the reference value was 6.0%. The excellent agreement demonstrates that the radon entry rate can be determined with consumer-grade detectors like RE+² (or others with similar response time and sensitivity) at typical indoor radon concentrations.

3.1.2. Radon entry rate determination in test-beds at SU

In Fig. 2 data series from the experiments at one of the test beds with open and closed ²²²Rn source are shown. The sessions with a closed source (e.g. in the region labelled “background” in Fig. 2(a) were used to determine the natural radon entry rate J_{bg} in the rooms. The radon entry rate determined in sessions with open source (e.g. in regions labelled “source” in Fig. 2(a) was considered the total entry rate J_{tot} . The achieved maximum activity concentrations were around 100 Bq/m³ - 200 Bq/m³ with closed source and 300 Bq/m³ - 600 Bq/m³ with open source. Such peak values are appropriate for simulating radon behaviour in buildings as they correspond to real concentrations in buildings above the limits recommended by WHO.

The data from almost all experimental sessions were successfully fitted and examples are shown in Fig. 2b–d. Some fits ended before the end of the session, which was explained by a change in the variables governing radon accumulation J and λ_{eff} (e.g. in Fig. 2d). We found that the natural entry rate J_{bg} in different sessions was positively correlated with λ_{eff} . To limit this influence, we only used sessions with λ_{eff} between 0.075 h⁻¹ and 0.124 h⁻¹. The entry rate of radon coming from the laboratory source J was estimated based on fits for these sessions as a difference of the means of J_{tot} and J_{bg} determined with open and closed source. The radon entry rate J estimated from the fits averaged for all detectors is compared with the reference value provided by the source certificate in Table 2. The highest relative difference of the value of J estimated by a separate detector and the reference value was less than 15.0%. The results clearly demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed method for realistic indoor environments.

3.2. Radon entry rate determination in field conditions: dwellings and workplaces

The results from the reference measurements in the PTB radon chamber and the test beds confirmed the applicability of the radon time series data provided by the RE+² detectors for determination of the radon entry rate at realistic indoor radon concentration. After the RE+² were shown to have sufficient sensitivity and response time, the data from the measurement campaign in dwellings and workplaces was analyzed. The ²²²Rn time series obtained from the long term monitoring were searched for intervals in which radon accumulates, which were fitted with Eq. (4). Examples of data series and successful estimates of the radon entry rate in occupied homes and workplaces are shown in Fig. 3. We consider a fit successful if its parameters are determined with uncertainty below 25% and the probability of not rejecting the fit by a chi-square test is higher than 0.5. The monitoring included rooms in a radon-priority area (the region of Buhovo [31]) and in an average-radon area (the city of Sofia [41]) with broad range of annual radon activity concentrations as shown in Fig. 4(a). More than 20 radon entry rate estimates were made in 25 rooms, which also represented different radon ranges as shown in Fig. 4(b). For these 25 rooms the radon entry rates per unit of floor area (J/S in Bq/m².h) were estimated by measuring the room height. The value of J/S allows comparison of the rooms when the dominant radon source is the ground or the floor material. The distributions of J/S are shown in Fig. 5(a) for the rooms in the Buhovo region and in Fig. 5(b) for the rooms in the Sofia region. The distributions of the radon decrease constant (λ_{eff}) are shown in Fig. 5(c). It is clear that the entry rate distributions for rooms in the Buhovo region reach higher values and have higher median than these for rooms in Sofia, while the ranges of λ_{eff} are comparable. The values of J/V (radon entry rate per unit volume) were of the order of tens of Bq/m³.h for the rooms in the Sofia region, where the annual average radon activity concentration was below 130 Bq/m³. They were of the order of hundreds of Bq/m³.h for the rooms in the Buhovo region where the annual average activity concentration was between several hundred and several thousand Bq/m³. These values are in agreement with values observed by other authors during normal building usage, even though different buildings in different regions are hard to compare. For example, in a remediated house with an average radon concentration of 135 Bq/m³ (measured from May to August), the radon entry rate was between 20 and 80 Bq/m³.h (reported in [11]). In an occupied house with radon concentration varying from 150 to 350 Bq/m³ the radon entry rate was estimated to vary between 40 and 100 Bq/m³.h (reported in [9]). In a basement with radon activity concentration varying from 500 to 5000 Bq/m³ the radon entry rate varied from 100 to 700 Bq/m³.h (reported in [10]).

In our study, data was suitable for determining the radon entry rate in all 10 buildings (out of the 36) where the annual average radon activity concentration exceeded 100 Bq/m³. In these buildings the data appropriate for fitting and applying the assumed model ranged from 4% to 20% of all data during normal operation of the buildings. In some monitored rooms, the frequency of successful fits varied across seasons. Typically, more increases were successfully fitted during seasons with higher indoor radon levels, when the counting statistics were more reliable. However, in certain cases, winter radon concentrations were constantly high, causing increases to start from a higher baseline and making them more difficult to fit reliably (e.g., Fig. 3e). As a result, data on J (such as in Fig. 5a and b) may only be indicative of the median and range of the radon entry rate. Rather than a precise measure, it should be interpreted as dynamic information on entry rates under different conditions and ventilation rates.

3.3. Correlation of radon entry rate and air change rate

The capability to estimate the entry rate of radon at different periods allows studying its dependence on other dynamic parameters. An example important for modelling radon transport in buildings and for radon mitigation planning is the dependence of the radon entry rate on

a

b

c

d

Fig. 1. (a) Data from the IRSd source during exposure 1 at PTB. The curves (top to bottom) show: the activity concentration of emanating radon, the radon activity retained in the source (right scale) and the corresponding counts in the detector (left scale); the radium activity of the source (right scale) and the corresponding counts (left scale), the calculated number of radon atoms η released from the source per second with its uncertainty at 1σ (shaded interval) and the relative humidity. (b) Increase of the activity concentration and its fits during the two exposures. The parameters of the fits are averaged over the results of the three detectors. (c), (d), Fitting of a single detector data during exposure 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1

Radon entry rate in the reference radon chamber given by the primary radon emanation standard J_{ref} and estimated by RE⁺² detectors J . The relative difference between J and J_{ref} is given in %. The numbers in parentheses are the absolute uncertainties ($k = 1$) referred to the corresponding last digits of the result.

²²² Rn source	Volume V, m ³	Ref. emanation rate J_{ref} , Bq/h	Meas. emanation rate J , Bq/h	Rel. difference Δ , %
IRSd 41-125F1	0.6744 (15)	0.2833 (76)	0.271 (13)	4.3
IRSd 44,589	0.6744 (15)	0.692 (15)	0.679 (26)	1.9

Fig. 2. Example of radon entry rate determination in a test bed experiment. (a) Radon concentration time series with opened source “source” and closed source “background”. (b), (d) Fits to determine the radon entry rate that is due to the source and background; (c) fit to determine the radon entry rate due to background, i.e. without source.

Table 2

Radon entry rates in two test beds at SU estimated for the radon source J_{ref} and by RE⁺² detectors J . The relative difference between J and J_{ref} is given in %. The numbers in parentheses are the absolute uncertainties (1 σ).

²²² Rn source	Volume V , m ³	Ref. emanation rate J_{ref} , Bq/h	Meas. emanation rate J , Bq/h	Rel. difference Δ , %
RF-100 flow-through	19.9 (13)	782 (12)	808 (53)	3.3
RF-100 flow-through	27.4 (16)	782 (12)	699 (41)	-11

the room ventilation rate. The ventilation rate can be characterized by the parameter air change rate per hour (ACH). Considering that the reference decay constant of radon [42] $\lambda = 0.007554 \text{ h}^{-1}$ is much smaller than the observed radon decrease constants, it can be assumed that the decrease of radon is mainly due to ventilation and $\text{ACH} \approx \lambda_{eff}$. We studied the correlation of J and ACH for each of the 32 rooms (out of the 36) with at least 10 measurements of the radon entry rate. While in some rooms the correlation was weak, in 25 out of 32 rooms there was positive correlation between the entry rate and the air change rate with coefficient of determination of the linear fit R^2 greater than 0.7 (in 17 rooms) and between 0.5 and 0.7 (in 8 rooms). Most of these rooms are ventilated naturally, but two of them have constant air conditioning. In one room the granite floor tiles have been identified as the main source of radon. A probable explanation for the correlation is that the increase in ventilation is either caused by or creates (in the case of forced ventilation) higher outdoor-indoor pressure difference, which also causes higher influx of radon from the soil gas and possibly from the building materials. An example of a case with strong correlation is given in Fig. 6(a) and with weak correlation in Fig. 6(b), along with plots of the activity concentration at saturation (C_A^∞) vs ACH. In rooms where J and ACH are positively correlated, C_A^∞ tends to stay constant when the air change rate increases (see Fig. 6c). This implies that radon activity concentration cannot be lowered below a specific value unless another mode of ventilation that decreases the pressure difference is added (e.g. mechanical ventilation with air intake). Similar behaviour of radon concentration in relation with the ventilation rate was noticed in separate dwellings by other authors [9] and predicted by modelling [43].

In some rooms the correlation between J and ACH was weak when all data was used. However, when the data was split by seasons very good correlations were found for some seasons as shown in Fig. 7. This

illustrates the fact that electronic radon monitors provide a unique opportunity to follow the radon entry rate in time and to compare its behaviour under different conditions.

3.4. Influence of the detector’s response function

The successful fitting and the fitting parameters could be influenced by the response function of the detectors used for monitoring. To study this effect, we simulated radon increases with different radon decrease constants λ_{eff} and the same value of J/V . Then, the simulated radon concentration was convoluted with the response function (see Eq.(7)) of the RE⁺² determined in [21] and fitted. Examples of the obtained fitting curves and their parameters for 4 and 12 hours of follow-up of the signal are shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b). The estimated values of the radon entry rate for simulated responses with different values of λ_{eff} are shown in Fig. 8(c). Naturally, the values are closer to the true value for smaller values of λ_{eff} corresponding to slower increases of the radon activity which are less influenced by the delay in the detector’s response. The uncertainty of J/V obtained by fitting is lower for increases that continue for longer periods. This simulation showed that for radon increases with $\lambda_{eff} < 1 \text{ h}^{-1}$ the bias in the values of J/V and λ_{eff} estimated by fitting was within 15% (see Fig. 8c and d). When the response function of the detector is not known, care should be taken to avoid fitting data with rise time smaller than the response time of the detector. The response time of the detector can be quantified in terms of the time necessary to reach 90% of the end signal after a sudden change in the radon activity concentration. For RE⁺² detectors this response time was estimated at 90 min [21]. A radon growth curve with $\lambda_{eff} = 1 \text{ h}^{-1}$ will reach 90% of its plateau after about 2.3 h. Increases with higher ventilation rate can be fitted if the parameters J and λ_{eff} stay constant

Fig. 3. (a),(b) Examples of year-long radon concentration time series in a home (a) and a workplace (b). (c),(e),(g), Radon concentration time series in homes (c, e) and a workplace (g) measured in region with average radon concentrations (c) and a radon-priority area (e, g). (d), (f), (h), Examples of fits with the radon model (the highlighted regions in (c), (e), (g), respectively). The radon accumulation parameters determined from the fits are given.

Fig. 4. (a) Number of studied rooms split by usage and location. The ranges of the yearly average radon activity concentrations for each type are given. (b) Percentage of rooms with successful radon entry rate measurements in the given interval. The bar on the right shows the percentage of rooms with radon activity concentration in the given intervals from all rooms with more than 20 radon entry rate measurements.

for sufficient time (several hours or more) and in rooms with higher radon activity concentration (e.g. in Fig. 3g). There are also laboratory grade monitors that have faster response time (like the AlphaGUARD

operating in flow-through mode) that could monitor faster increases. Some of the consumer-grade monitors on the other hand, have slower response [32,35] than the RE⁺² and might not be suitable for entry rate

Fig. 5. (a), (b) Violin plots of the distribution of J/S (radon entry rate per unit of room floor area) of all conducted measurements in different homes and workplaces in the city of Sofia (a) and in the region of Buhovo (b). (c) Box plots of the distribution of λ_{eff} for all measurements. The measurements in Sofia are shown with orange and in Buhovo with blue. All middle horizontal bars represent the medians of the distributions. All colored regions represent the interquartile range and the whiskers are at 1.5 times the interquartile range from each side of the colored region. The circles represent the outliers outside the whiskers. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. (a),(b) Dependence of J/V on the air change rate ACH (i.e. on λ_{eff}) estimated by RE⁺² measurements of the radon entry rate in homes. The equation of the linear fit and its coefficient of determination (R) are given. (c),(d) Dependence of the activity concentration of radon at saturation C_A^∞ on the ACH for the corresponding measurements in (a) and (b). The measurements in different seasons are presented with different color. All error bars represent the uncertainty of the fitting parameters at the level of 1 σ . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

monitoring. A more detailed analysis of the uncertainties of the fitting parameters, including the influence of the statistical uncertainty of the data, is planned for future studies.

4. Discussion

In order to demonstrate the inherent characteristics of the proposed approach, two examples of successful determinations of the radon source term by our algorithm are provided in Fig. 9. The data in the plots contain the radon activity concentration, as well as the indoor temperature and humidity measured by the REs, and several other environmental parameters measured simultaneously by Netatmo sensors installed indoors at the same room and close to the room outdoors. These parameters are: indoor temperature, relative humidity, pressure and CO₂ concentration and outdoor temperature and relative humidity.

From the results in Fig. 9, it is immediately evident that the regions found suitable by the algorithm for determining the radon entry rate are characterized by stable indoor temperature and humidity. The typical variations of these parameters observed outside the fitting region are not seen during the period of the fit. We interpret this as a clear indication that the proposed method identifies regions in the time series with stable indoor conditions. As discussed in [44], the variation in indoor parameters is among the main factors causing variation on the air change rate. The variation of the ratio of indoor and outdoor temperature might also have influence [44], but it is limited in the regions where the fit reproduces the data well.

Our interpretation of the examples is as follows: when the house or apartment has been ventilated and then closed for some time (e.g., family leaving for the weekend or holiday), the indoor conditions exhibit

Fig. 7. (a), Dependence of J/V on the air change rate ACH (i.e. on λ_{eff}) estimated by RE⁺2 measurements of the radon entry rate in a home in radon-priority area. The equation of the linear fit and its coefficient of determination (R) are given. (b) Dependence of the activity concentration of radon at saturation C_A^∞ on the ACH for the corresponding measurements in (a). The data points in different seasons are presented with different colour. (c)–(f), The data and the fits in (a) split by season. All error bars represent the uncertainty of the fitting parameters at the level of 1 σ . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. (a),(b) Examples of simulations of the signal from RE⁺2 detector obtained by convolution of the theoretical radon increase and the detector’s response function. The simulated signal is fitted with the function in Eq. (3) and the fit parameters are estimated. (c) Values and uncertainties of J/V estimated by fitting for different λ_{eff} and 4- and 12-hour follow-up of the increase. The true value of J/V is 100 Bq/m³.h (dashed line). (d) Relative difference between the simulated and the estimated by fitting value of λ_{eff} for different simulated λ_{eff} .

a

b

Fig. 9. Example time-series of indoor and outdoor air parameters during the intervals selected for determination of the radon entry rate during the winter (a) and spring (b). From top to bottom: radon activity concentration by RE⁺², indoor temperature, relative humidity, CO₂ concentration and pressure determined by NetAtmo meteorological station at the same room, outdoor temperature and humidity by NetAtmo outdoor module at the same location and inner temperature and humidity reported by RE⁺². The region of the successful fit with the theoretical model (filled region) is characterized by stability of the indoor parameters.

stable humidity, temperature, pressure, and even CO₂ concentration, implying a stable air change rate (ACH). Therefore, even though we are dealing with non-organized and non-modified habits of the occupants and natural ventilation, our approach successfully identifies the

time slots of stable parameters in the time-series, allowing the estimate of the radon entry rate.

The radon entry rate (or radon source term) in buildings has previously been estimated only in case studies focusing on one or several

buildings with elevated radon levels [9–13,17,19]. In some studies, the air change rate was measured independently (often using a tracer gas), and the radon entry rate was estimated as the product of the air change rate and the current radon activity concentration [9–12], analogous to Eq. (5). However, this estimate is only approximate, as the current radon activity is often not at saturation and does not represent C_A^∞ . More recent studies have estimated the radon entry rate by evacuating, sealing, and depressurizing houses [13,17–19], using the maximum radon activity concentration reached under these conditions. These case studies demonstrate the importance of measuring the radon entry rate for evaluating potential mitigation strategies [10,11] or assessing the effects of ventilation rates [9,16], energy retrofiting [18] and environmental factors such as wind, rain, and barometric pressure [12] on indoor radon levels. However, such measurements have been scarce, likely due to the need for expensive radon detectors, additional air change rate measurements, and/or special procedures in the building. In contrast, our study demonstrates that certain electronic detectors designed for end-users can provide data for reasonably precise estimation of indoor radon entry rates. Furthermore, our findings from homes and workplaces indicate that the radon entry rate can be measured during normal use without disrupting occupants' daily routines. This allows for unbiased estimates under everyday conditions. The rapid adoption of electronic radon monitors in many countries may facilitate the accumulation of data on a quantity that has rarely been measured until now. Such data might be invaluable for improving radon mitigation strategies, understanding radon entry rate and identifying at-risk buildings.

In buildings with high radon levels and radon mitigation systems, the data on the radon entry rate could show the efficiency in isolating the sources of radon. Up to now the efficiency of radon mitigation measures and installations has been estimated by the achieved reduction in radon activity concentration. The availability of simultaneous estimates of the air change rate can facilitate analyses of the energy cost of anti-radon measures. Our approach can also be invaluable in the planning of radon mitigation. The pre-mitigation diagnostics involve investigation of the pressure differences, the air tightness of the building and planning of the required ventilation rate [2]. In buildings with mechanical ventilation it is in fact recommended to use continuous radon monitors to estimate the effect of the ventilation on radon concentrations [2]. Such analyses are straightforward when one can simultaneously determine radon concentration, radon entry rate and air change rate as with our approach (see the examples in Fig. 6). The continuation of online radon monitoring after the mitigation can further help to detect and analyze flaws or deterioration of the installation.

Another straightforward application of our approach is the validation of models describing radon entry into buildings. Numerous such models have been developed [8], most of which aim to characterize radon generation and transport through soil, as well as its entry into buildings. These models consider a wide range of parameters, including soil composition and moisture, building construction and radon entry pathways, and environmental factors such as indoor-outdoor temperature differences, wind speed, and wind direction, which drive pressure gradients [6]. Some models also account for radon exhalation from building materials and its emanation from water and natural gas [24]. The radon entry rate is a key output of these models, allowing for direct comparison between them [45]. Additionally, some models incorporate radon sinks (i.e. outlets) and radon's distribution within the buildings to predict indoor radon activity concentration and, in some cases, its variation over time. Currently, model validation relies solely on comparisons with indoor radon activity concentration measurements [24,46]. The experimental results obtained through our approach—specifically, radon entry rates and air change rates—could enhance model validation and adaptation. These models are valuable not only for understanding radon transport and designing mitigation strategies, but also for identifying factors contributing to high indoor radon levels.

The accumulation of data on radon entry rate in various rooms and buildings could also empower the efforts to find more buildings with

elevated radon levels. Statistical and machine learning techniques have been used to pinpoint buildings with potential radon problem based on their characteristics and geographical and geological factors (see [47] and the references therein). These efforts are justified by the fact that a great number of affected buildings are located outside the radon priority areas [48] in which the majority of radon measurements are concentrated. In European legislation [49] radon priority areas are defined as areas where a significant number of buildings is expected to exceed the national reference level, without taking into account the population density. Therefore, building-focused predictions could help to optimize measurement campaigns. The models used for predictions are trained and tested with the long-term average radon activity concentration as response variable (i.e. the quantity to be predicted or classified), which is considered representative for the lung cancer risk [2] and is used in normative documents. The addition of the radon entry rate as a response variable could improve the performance of the models. Our hypothesis is that the radon entry rate is more related to the physical factors than a long-term integral value like the average radon concentration. This hypothesis still has to be tested with a large number and variety of buildings.

There are several limitations of the proposed method. The radon entry rate can be determined only in intervals with favourable stable conditions, e.g. stable ventilation rate while the occupants are absent for the day or the weekend or are sleeping during the night. This approach is incapable to capture the variability in the radon entry rate under changing conditions. In some buildings several months of data might be needed to find appropriate time slots for determination of J when no prearrangement is made with the occupants. As discussed above, the results might not be representative of the average or the extreme radon entry rate, but rather shows its variation. Moreover, in order to have successful fits at higher ventilation rates only detectors with fast response time should be used (e.g. less than 2 h response time for air change rate of 1 h^{-1}). Another limitation is related to the low statistics and potential bias of the measurements with consumer-grade radon detectors. At 100 Bq/m^3 the standard deviation of RadonEye + 2 results is about 10% and their bias can reach 30% when not calibrated [37,38]. That is why, only individually calibrated monitors were used in the current study. In cases where precise measurements are necessary more sensitive and reliable high-grade electronic radon detectors could be used. There is also potential to apply the proposed method by performing parallel measurement of the ventilation rate (e.g. with a tracer gas [14,18]) and estimate only one parameter from fitting the radon time series. Overall, our approach has the potential to address contemporary challenges in radiation protection, which include estimating the impact on indoor radon levels of energy-efficient renovations [50–53], shared ventilation in large buildings [54], and increased use of air conditioning for cooling, possibly related to climate change [55].

5. Conclusions

Radon entry rate and air change rate were successfully estimated remotely in 36 occupied rooms in homes and workplaces with a wide range of radon activity concentrations using affordable radon detectors available on the market. A simple model was used to fit the intervals in the obtained radon time series in which radon accumulates under stable conditions and to estimate the radon entry rate and the air change rate. The approach was tested in experiments in a primary metrology laboratory and radon test-beds and very good agreement was observed between the estimated and the reference values of the radon entry rate.

The accumulation of dynamic data on the radon entry rate, can help researchers and building engineers to better understand the mechanisms driving changes in radon concentration under different conditions. This was illustrated by studying the correlation between the radon entry rate and the air change rate measured simultaneously, which was very strong in 80% of the rooms for ACH below 1 h^{-1} .

This new approach provides insights into radon dynamics and can revolutionize our efforts to maintain healthy indoor environment with respect to radon. It has the potential to change the design and operation of mitigation systems by providing information on the actual dynamic parameters governing radon accumulation. Furthermore, the gathered information on radon entry rate can be invaluable for validating and improving models of radon transport in buildings as well as for approaches for prediction of buildings with high radon risk by mapping and AI technologies. Our findings could support the development of new technologies to manage radon exposure while also addressing indoor air quality and energy efficiency in tune with the modern comprehensive approaches [56].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Krasimir Mitev: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Vladislav Todorov:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Strahil Georgiev:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Philippe Cassette:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Benoit Sabot:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Zornitza Daraktchieva:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Stefan Röttger:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ivelina Dimitrova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work is financed by the European Union NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No. BG-RRP-2.004–0008-C01.

The study received support from the project RadonNET (23IND07) which was funded by the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States. Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] J. Gaskin, D. Coyle, J. Whyte, D. Krewski, Global estimate of lung cancer mortality attributable to residential radon, *Environ. Health Perspect.* 126 (5) (2018) 057009, <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP2503>
- [2] World Health Organization, WHO Handbook on Indoor Radon - A Public Health Perspective, 2009, <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241547673>
- [3] S. Darby, D. Hill, A. Auvinen, J.M. Barros-Dios, H. Baysson, F. Bochicchio, H. Deo, R. Falk, F. Forastiere, M. Hakama, I. Heid, L. Kreienbrock, M. Kreuzer, F. Lagarde, I. Mäkeläinen, C. Muirhead, W. Oberaigner, G. Pershagen, A. Ruano-Ravina, E. Ruosteenoja, A.S. Rosario, M. Tirmarche, L. Tomáscaronjek, E. Whitley, H.-E. Wichmann, R. Doll, Radon in homes and risk of lung cancer: collaborative analysis of individual data from 13 European case-control studies, *BMJ* 330 (7485) (2005) 223, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.38308.477650.63>
- [4] A.C. George, The history, development and the present status of the radon measurement programme in the United States of America, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 167 (1–3) (2015) 8–14, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncv213>
- [5] RadonLeaders, National Radon Action Plan 2021–2025, 2022, www.radonleaders.org/resources/nationalradonactionplan
- [6] W.W. Nazaroff, Radon transport from soil to AIR, *Rev. Geophys.* 30 (1992) 137–160, <https://doi.org/10.1029/92RG00055>
- [7] U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), Consumer's Guide to Radon Reduction How to Fix Your Home Indoor. EPA-402-K10-005, 2016, https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2016-12/documents/2016_consumers_guide_to_radon_reduction.pdf
- [8] A.J. Gadgil, Models of radon entry, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 45 (1–4) (1991) 373–379, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/45.1-4.373>
- [9] W.W. Nazaroff, H. Feustel, A.V. Nero, K.L. Revzan, D.T. Grimsrud, M.A. Essling, R.E. Toohay, Radon transport into a detached one-story house with a basement, *Atmos. Environ.* (1967) 19 (1) (1985) 31–46, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981\(85\)90134-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981(85)90134-9)
- [10] A. Cavallo, K. Gadsby, T.A. Reddy, Use of natural basement ventilation to control radon in single family dwellings, *Atmos. Environ. Part A Gen. Top.* 26 (12) (1992) 2251–2256, fifth International Conference on Indoor Air Quality and Climate Indoor Air '90: Characterization of Indoor Air. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-1686\(92\)90415-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-1686(92)90415-H)
- [11] H. Kokotti, T. Keskkuru, P. Kalliokoski, Radon mitigation with pressure-controlled mechanical ventilation, *Build. Environ.* 29 (3) (1994) 387–392, special Issue Papers from Indoor Air '93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323\(94\)90039-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323(94)90039-6), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360132394900396>
- [12] T. Keskkuru, H. Kokotti, S. Lammi, P. Kalliokoski, Effect of various factors on the rate of radon entry into two different types of houses, *Build. Environ.* 36 (10) (2001) 1091–1098, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323\(00\)00077-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323(00)00077-9)
- [13] W. Ringer, H. Kaineder, F.-J. Maringer, P. Kindl, Determination of the radon potential of a building by a controlled depressurisation technique (racode), in: *The Natural Radiation Environment VII: VIIIth Int. Symp. On the NRE, Vol. 7 of Radioactivity in the Environment*, Elsevier, 2005, pp. 221–231, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-4860\(04\)07025-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-4860(04)07025-1)
- [14] M. Brabec, K. Jilek, State-space dynamic model for estimation of radon entry rate, based on kalman filtering, *J. Environ. Radioact.* 98 (3) (2007) 285–297, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2007.05.006>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0265931X07001245>
- [15] M. Brabec, K. Jilek, Dynamical model for indoor radon concentration monitoring, *Environmetrics* 20 (2009) 718–729, <https://doi.org/10.1002/env.973>
- [16] A. Froňka, K. Jilek, L. Moučka, M. Brabec, Significance of independent radon entry rate and AIR exchange rate assessment for the purpose of radon mitigation effectiveness proper evaluation: case studies, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 145 (2–3) (2011) 133–137, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncr051>
- [17] B. Collignan, C. Lorkowski, R. Améon, Development of a methodology to characterize radon entry in dwellings, *Build. Environ.* 57 (2012) 176–183, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2012.05.002>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360132312001503>
- [18] A. Froňka, K. Jilek, Radon entry rate analyses using in situ tracer gas method application, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 160 (1–3) (2014) 143–148, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncu074>
- [19] J.A. McGrath, M.A. Byrne, An approach to predicting indoor radon concentration based on depressurisation measurements, *Ind. Built Environ.* 30 (8) (2021) 1042–1050, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1420326X20924747>
- [20] P. McNall, et al., Indoor AIR Quality Modeling Phase i Report Framework for Development of General Models NBSIR 85-3265, 1985, <https://doi.org/10.6028/NBS.IR.85-3265>
- [21] I. Dimitrova, S. Georgiev, K. Mitev, V. Todorov, C. Dutsov, B. Sabot, Study of the performance and time response of the Radoneye plus2 continuous radon monitor, *Measurement* 207 (2023) 112409, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2022.112409>
- [22] J.A. Gunby, S.C. Darby, J.C. Miles, B.M. Green, D.R. Cox, Factors affecting indoor radon concentrations in the United Kingdom, *Health Phys.* 64 (1) (1993) 2, <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004032-199301000-00001>
- [23] D. Pressyanov, S. Georgiev, I. Dimitrova, K. Mitev, T. Boshkova, Determination of the diffusion coefficient and solubility of radon in plastics, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 145 (2–3) (2011) 123–126, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncr069>
- [24] L. Font, C. Baixeras, The Ragena dynamic model of radon generation, entry and accumulation indoors, *Sci. Total Environ.* 307 (1) (2003) 55–69, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697\(02\)00462-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697(02)00462-X)
- [25] I. Čeliković, G. Pantelić, I. Vukanac, J.K. Nikolić, M. Živanović, G. Cinelli, V. Gruber, S. Baumann, G. Ciotoli, L.S.Q. Poncela, D. Rábago, Overview of radon flux characteristics, measurements, models and its potential use for the estimation of radon priority areas, *Atmosphere* 13 (12) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13122005>
- [26] N. Jonassen, The determination of radon exhalation rates, *Health Phys.* 45 (2) (1983) 369–376, <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004032-198308000-00009>
- [27] C.Y.H. Chao, T.C.W. Tung, D.W.T. Chan, J. Burnett, Determination of radon emanation and back diffusion characteristics of building materials in small chamber tests, *Build. Environ.* 32 (4) (1997) 355–362, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323\(96\)00071-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323(96)00071-6)
- [28] F. Mertes, S. Röttger, A. Röttger, Approximate sequential Bayesian filtering to estimate ²²²Rn emanation from ²²⁶Ra sources using spectral time series, *J. Sens. Syst.* 12 (1) (2023) 147–161, <https://doi.org/10.5194/jsss-12-147-2023>, <https://jsss.copernicus.org/articles/12/147/2023/>
- [29] F. Mertes, S. Röttger, A. Röttger, Development of ²²²Rn emanation sources with integrated quasi 2π active monitoring, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 19 (2) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020840>
- [30] K. Mitev, S. Georgiev, I. Dimitrova, V. Todorov, A. Popova, C. Dutsov, B. Sabot, Recent work with electronic radon detectors for continuous radon-222 monitoring, *J. Eur. Radon Assoc.* 3 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.35815/radon.v3.8844>
- [31] D. Pressyanov, I. Dimitrova, K. Mitev, S. Georgiev, D. Dimitrov, Identifying radon priority areas and dwellings with radon exceedances in Bulgaria using stored Cd/dvds, *J. Environ. Radioact.* 196 (2019) 274–280, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2017.11.022>
- [32] T.R. Beck, E. Foerster, M. Biel, S. Feige, Measurement performance of electronic radon monitors, *Atmosphere* 15 (10) (2024) <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4433/15/10/1180>

- [33] Z. Daraktchieva, C.B. Howarth, J.M. Wasikiewicz, C.A. Miller, D.A. Wright, Long-term comparison and performance study of consumer grade electronic radon integrating monitors, *J. Radiol. Prot.* 44 (3) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6498/ad66db>
- [34] RadonFTLab, Radoneye plus2 detector description, <http://radonftlab.com/radon-sensor-product/radon-detector/new-rd200p-radon-detector>
- [35] D. Rábago, E. Fernández, S. Celaya, I. Fuente, A. Fernández, J. Quindós, R. Rodriguez, L. Quindós, C. Sainz, Investigation of the performance of various low-cost radon monitors under variable environmental conditions, *Sensors* 24 (6) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24061836>
- [36] J.F. Rey, N. Meisser, D. Licina, J. Goyette Pernot, Performance evaluation of radon active sensors and passive dosimeters at low and high radon concentrations, *Build. Environ.* 250 (2024) 111154, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.111154>
- [37] J.F. Rey, D. Licina, J. Goyette Pernot, Performance evaluation of radon measurement techniques in single-family homes, *Indoor Environ.* 2 (2025) 100087, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indenv.2025.100087>
- [38] I. Dimitrova, S. Georgiev, V. Todorov, Z. Daraktchieva, C.B. Howarth, J.M. Wasikiewicz, B. Sabot, K. Mitev, Calibration and metrological test of the Radoneye plus2 electronic monitor, *Radiat. Meas.* 175 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2024.107169>
- [39] P. Virtanen, R. Gommers, T.E. Oliphant, M. Haberland, T. Reddy, D. Cournapeau, E. Burovski, P. Peterson, W. Weckesser, J. Bright, S.J. van der Walt, M. Brett, J. Wilson, K.J. Millman, N. Mayorov, A.R.J. Nelson, E. Jones, R. Kern, E. Larson, C.J. Carey, Í. Polat, Y. Feng, E.W. Moore, J. VanderPlas, D. Laxalde, J. Perktold, R. Cimrman, I. Henriksen, E.A. Quintero, C.R. Harris, A.M. Archibald, A.H. Ribeiro, F. Pedregosa, P. van Mulbregt, SciPy 1.0 Contributors, Scipy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python, *Nat. Methods* 17 (2020) 261–272, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2>
- [40] S. Röttger, A. Röttger, F. Mertes, V. Morosch, T. Ballé, S. Chambers, Evolution of traceable radon emanation sources from mbq to few bq, *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 196 (2023) 110726, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2023.110726>
- [41] K. Ivanova, Z. Stojanovska, B. Kunovska, N. Chobanova, V. Badulin, A. Benderev, Analysis of the spatial variation of indoor radon concentrations (national survey in Bulgaria), *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 26 (7) (2019) 6971–6979.
- [42] M.-M. Bé, V. Chisté, C. Dulieu, E. Browne, V. Chechev, N. Kuzmenko, F. Kondev, A. Luca, M. Galán, A. Pearce, X. Huang, Monographie BIPM-5: Table of Radionuclides, vol. 4, Bureau International Des Poids Et Mesures, France, 2008, ISBN: 92-822-2230-6. <https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/monographies>
- [43] L. Font, Radon Generation, Entry and Accumulation Indoors, (Ph.D. thesis), Niversitat Auto'noma de Barcelona, 1997.
- [44] D. Markov, Modeling of indoor AIR composition time variation during the night in naturally ventilated occupied spaces, *J. Univ. Rousse* 51 (1.2) (2012) 60–65.
- [45] C.E. Andersen, E. al., Erricca radon model intercomparison exercise, 1999, https://inis.iaea.org/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/30/022/30022940.pdf
- [46] M. Mancini, S. Guida, A. Cuomo, D. Guida, A.H. Ismail, Modelling of indoor radon activity concentration dynamics and its validation through in-situ measurements on regional scale, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 1982 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5045449>
- [47] P.-Y. Wu, T. Johansson, C. Sandels, M. Mangold, K. Mjörnell, Indoor radon interval prediction in the Swedish building stock using machine learning, *Build. Environ.* 245 (2023) 110879, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110879>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S036013232300906X>
- [48] E. Petermann, P. Bossew, B. Hoffmann, Radon hazard VS. Radon risk - on the effectiveness of radon priority areas, *J. Environ. Radioact.* 244-245 (2022) 106833, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2022.106833>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0265931X22000236>
- [49] Council directive 2013/59/EURATOM of 5 December 2013 laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation, 2013, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2013/59/oj>
- [50] I. Fojtikova, K. Navratilova Rovenska, Influence of energy-saving measures on the radon concentration in some kindergartens in the Czech Republic, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 160 (1–3) (2014) 149–153, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncu073>
- [51] M. Jiránek, V. Kačmaříková, Dealing with the increased radon concentration in thermally retrofitted buildings, *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 160 (1–3) (2014) 43–47, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncu104>
- [52] D. Pressyanov, D. Dimitrov, I. Dimitrova, Energy-efficient reconstructions and indoor radon: the impact assessed by cds/dvds, *J. Environ. Radioact.* 143 (2015) 76–79, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2015.02.016>
- [53] P. Symonds, D. Rees, Z. Daraktchieva, N. McColl, J. Bradley, I. Hamilton, M. Davies, Home energy efficiency and radon: an observational study, *Indoor Air* 29 (5) (2019) 854–864, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ina.12575>
- [54] S. Florica, A. Lupulescu, T. Dicu, A.C. Tenter, M. Moldovan, G. Dobrei, L. Copaci, A. Cucos, Radon concentration assessment in urban Romanian buildings: a multistory analysis, *Atmosphere* 15 (11) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15111267>
- [55] F.K.T. Stanley, J.L. Irvine, W.R. Jacques, S.R. Salgia, D.G. Innes, B.D. Winquist, D.R.B. David Torr, A.A. Goodarzi, Radon exposure is rising steadily within the modern North American residential environment, and is increasingly uniform across seasons, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (2019) 18472, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-54891-8>
- [56] B.D. Burghel, M. Botoș, S. Beldean-Galea, A. Cucos, T. Catalina, T. Dicu, G. Dobrei, Ș. Florică, A. Istrate, A. Lupulescu, M. Moldovan, D. Niță, B. Papp, I. Pap, K. Szacsvai, C. Sainz, A. Tunyagi, A. Tenter, Comprehensive survey on radon mitigation and indoor AIR quality in energy efficient buildings from Romania, *Sci. Total Environ.* 751 (2021) 141858, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141858>